

Active Fuzzy Control of Linear and Nonlinear Suspensions in Vehicles

Konstantinos Marakakis^{1,2}, Manolis Paterakis¹, Georgios K. Tairidis¹, Georgios E. Stavroulakis^{*1}

¹ School of Production and Management, Technical University of Crete, GR-73100 Chania, Greece

² IKTEO Chanion – Technical Inspection Site for Vehicles, Chania, Greece

* Corresponding Author: gestavroulakis@tuc.gr

Abstract

Suspensions are vital for a vehicle, since they provide safety and comfort. There are many types of suspensions in the industry. The most advanced of them are the active or electronic suspensions, where the degree of damping is modified in order to achieve the desired rolling of the vehicle. This is achieved by changing the pressure or the flow of air or oil inside the damper, or its properties. A control system is necessary for this task. Powerful and robust soft control tools, such as fuzzy inference systems can provide the desired results. In the present paper, the active suspension is controlled by a fuzzy logic controller through a piezoelectric actuator which provides the control force. Classical control tools, such as the Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller are used for comparison. From the simulation results it is shown that both methods can achieve smooth behaviour of the active suspension. Fuzzy control was proved to be faster than the PID, while the latter was more efficient in the first period of vibration. Moreover, the fuzzy controller was proved very efficient even in the presence of non-linearities within the suspension system.

Keywords: Fuzzy control; active suspension; vehicle dynamics; PID control.

1. Introduction

Suspensions are vital for a vehicle, since they provide safety and comfort. There are many types of suspensions in the industry. The most advanced of them are the active or electronic suspensions, where the degree of damping is modified in order to achieve the desired rolling of the vehicle. This is achieved by changing the pressure or the flow of air or oil inside the damper, or its properties. A control system is necessary for this task. Powerful and robust soft control tools, such as fuzzy inference systems can provide the desired results.

In the present paper, the active suspension is controlled by a fuzzy logic controller through a piezoelectric actuator which provides the control force. Classical control tools, such as the Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller are used for comparison. From the simulation results it is shown that both methods can achieve smooth behavior of the active suspension. Fuzzy control was proved to be faster than the PID, while the latter was more efficient in the first period of vibration. Moreover,

the fuzzy controller was proved very efficient even in the presence of non-linearities within the suspension system.

2. Materials and methods

A simplified model of a smart suspension is used and fuzzy, PID and nonlinear controllers are developed and compared on it. The work can be extended to more complicated half-car or full-vehicle models.

2.1 Active suspension systems

The design and modelling of an active suspension system of a vehicle constitutes an interesting automated control problem. In the present investigation, a quarter-vehicle suspension model, that is, one of the four wheels will be considered. Two different configurations were considered for the suspension system: one with linear spring and one with non-linear spring. The quarter car with the linear and nonlinear suspension is depicted in Figure 1. The quarter vehicle concept simplifies the problem to a two-degree-of-freedom spring-mass-damper dynamic problem. For the linear problem, the equations of motion are given by Newton's second law of motion in terms of generalized coordinates as:

$$m_1\ddot{x}_1 = -k_1(x_1 - x_2) - b_1(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2) + u \quad (1)$$

$$m_2\ddot{x}_2 = k_1(x_1 - x_2) + k_2(w - x_2) + b_1(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2) + b_2(\dot{w} - \dot{x}_2) - u \quad (2)$$

The equations of motion for suspension system with a quadratic nonlinearity are given by:

$$m_1\ddot{x}_1 = -k_1(x_1 - x_2) - k'_1(x_1 - x_2)^2 - b_1(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2) + u \quad (3)$$

$$m_2\ddot{x}_2 = k_1(x_1 - x_2) + k'_1(x_1 - x_2)^2 + k_2(w - x_2) + b_1(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2) + b_2(\dot{w} - \dot{x}_2) - u \quad (4)$$

In Equations 1-4 with m_1 is denoted the mass of the quarter-vehicle, while m_2 is the mass of the whole system of the wheel (including steering, suspension, etc). Also, k_1 is the linear spring constant of the suspension system, k_2 is the spring constant of the wheel, b_1 is the damping constant of the suspension system and b_2 is the damping constant of the wheel. With x_1 is represented the deflection of the vehicle, x_2 is the deflection of the suspension system, and the first and second derivatives of them are the respective velocities and accelerations. With u is denoted the control actuator force, while w is the disturbance from the road. In Equations 3 and 4 with k'_1 is denoted the nonlinear spring constant. For the present study, the masses, spring constants and damping constants are selected as $m_1=500\text{kg}$, $m_2=200\text{kg}$, $k_1= 70500 \text{ N/m}$, $k_2= 150000 \text{ N/m}$, $b_1= 370 \text{ N}\cdot\text{s/m}$ and $b_2= 8620 \text{ N}\cdot\text{s/m}$. The constant $k'_1= 110000 \text{ N/m}$. Two different types of disturbance (road abnormalities) were studied: one of step form where $w= -0.1\text{m}$ and one of sinusoidal form where $w(t)= -0.1\cdot\sin(t)-0.1\text{m}$.

Figure 1. The quarter-vehicle suspension model.

2.2 Fuzzy control

A Mamdani-type fuzzy controller is developed within the MATLAB environment, using the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox. The inputs of the controller are deflection, velocity and acceleration, while the output of control is the actuator force which is necessary for the control of the active suspension. The membership functions of fuzzy variables were selected by engineer's intuition and experience and are depicted in Figure 2. The range of the first and the second input variables, that is deflection and velocity is $[-1, 1]$ and five membership functions (categories), namely, Negative Medium (NM), Negative Small (NS), Zero (ZE), Positive Small (PS) and Positive Medium (PM) are considered for both variables. For the third input, that is, the acceleration, the range is $[-0.1, 0.1]$ and three membership function are considered; Negative (N), Zero (ZE) and Positive (P). The output variable (actuator force) has a range of values in the interval $[-5000, 5000]$ and nine membership functions are used; Negative Very big (NV), Negative Big (NB), Negative Medium (NM), Negative Small (NS), Zero (ZE), Positive Small (PS), Positive Medium (PM), Positive Big (PB) and Positive Very big (PV).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 2. (a) Membership function of deflection; (b) Membership function of velocity; (c) Membership function of acceleration; (d) Membership function of actuator force.

The rule-base is written considering the movement of a pendulum. The number of rules which are necessary for the decision-making unit of the fuzzy system is derived according to the number of input variables and its membership functions. In the present controller, 50 if-then rules are used for the description of the fuzzy system. These verbal

rules are given in Table 1. If necessary (e.g. for real-time applications) the third input can be removed and this data-base will be reduced to 25 rules.

Table 1. The fuzzy inference system, linguistic if-then rules.

Rule	$x_1 - x_2$	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$	F	Rule	$x_1 - x_2$	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$	F
R ₁	PM	PM	ZE	ZE ¹	R ₂₆	PM	PM	not ZE	NS
R ₂	PS	PM	ZE	NS	R ₂₇	PS	PM	not ZE	NM
R ₃	ZE	PM	ZE	NM	R ₂₈	ZE	PM	not ZE	NB
R ₄	NS	PM	ZE	NM	R ₂₉	NS	PM	not ZE	NB
R ₅	NM	PM	ZE	NB	R ₃₀	NM	PM	not ZE	NV
R ₆	PM	PS	ZE	ZE	R ₃₁	PM	PS	not ZE	NS
R ₇	PS	PS	ZE	NS	R ₃₂	PS	PS	not ZE	NM
R ₈	ZE	PS	ZE	NS	R ₃₃	ZE	PS	not ZE	NM
R ₉	NS	PS	ZE	NM	R ₃₄	NS	PS	not ZE	NB
R ₁₀	NM	PS	ZE	NM	R ₃₅	NM	PS	not ZE	NB
R ₁₁	PM	ZE	ZE	PS	R ₃₆	PM	ZE	not ZE	PM
R ₁₂	PS	ZE	ZE	ZE	R ₃₇	PS	ZE	not ZE	PS
R ₁₃	ZE	ZE	ZE	ZE	R ₃₈	ZE	ZE	not ZE	ZE
R ₁₄	NS	ZE	ZE	ZE	R ₃₉	NS	ZE	not ZE	NS
R ₁₅	NM	ZE	ZE	NS	R ₄₀	NM	ZE	not ZE	NM
R ₁₆	PM	NS	ZE	PM	R ₄₁	PM	NS	not ZE	PB
R ₁₇	PS	NS	ZE	PM	R ₄₂	PS	NS	not ZE	PB
R ₁₈	ZE	NS	ZE	PS	R ₄₃	ZE	NS	not ZE	PM
R ₁₉	NS	NS	ZE	PS	R ₄₄	NS	NS	not ZE	PM
R ₂₀	NM	NS	ZE	ZE	R ₄₅	NM	NS	not ZE	PS
R ₂₁	PM	NM	ZE	PB	R ₄₆	PM	NM	not ZE	PV
R ₂₂	PS	NM	ZE	PM	R ₄₇	PS	NM	not ZE	PB
R ₂₃	ZE	NM	ZE	PM	R ₄₈	ZE	NM	not ZE	PB
R ₂₄	NS	NM	ZE	PS	R ₄₉	NS	NM	not ZE	PM
R ₂₅	NM	NM	ZE	ZE	R ₅₀	NM	NM	not ZE	PS

¹ e.g. Rule 1: If the Deflection X_1-X_2 is Positive Medium and the Velocity V_1-V_2 is Positive Medium and the Acceleration A_1-A_2 is Zero, then the Actuator Force is Zero.

The graphic representation (surface) of the rules for the three inputs and the one output is depicted in pairs of inputs over the output as shown in Figure 3.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3. Fuzzy surface for (a) deflection-velocity; (b) deflection-acceleration; (c) velocity-acceleration.

2.3 PID control

A PID controller is developed in order to check the efficiency of the control for the linear case. In order to apply the PID controller to the system, the transfer function of the plant (suspension model) and the disturbance (road abnormalities) are necessary to be calculated. Considering that all the initial conditions are zero, that is, the moment that the wheel of the vehicle receives a disturbance from the road, Equations 1 and 2 can be reformed through Laplace transformation giving the transfer functions $G_1(s)$ and $G_2(s)$ with output x_1-x_2 and inputs u and w , as follows

$$(m_1s^2 + b_1s + k_1)X_1(s) - (b_1s + k_1)X_2(s) = U(s) \quad (5)$$

$$-(b_1s + k_1)X_1(s) + (m_2s^2 + (b_1 + b_2)s + (k_1 + k_2))X_2(s) = (b_2s + k_2)W(s) - U(s) \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} (m_1s^2 + b_1s + k_1) & -(b_1s + k_1) \\ -(b_1s + k_1) & (m_2s^2 + (b_1 + b_2)s + (k_1 + k_2)) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X_1(s) \\ X_2(s) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U(s) \\ (b_2s + k_2)W(s) - U(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Let us say that

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} (m_1s^2 + b_1s + k_1) & -(b_1s + k_1) \\ -(b_1s + k_1) & (m_2s^2 + (b_1 + b_2)s + (k_1 + k_2)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta = \det(A) = (m_1s^2 + b_1s + k_1) \cdot (m_2s^2 + (b_1 + b_2)s + (k_1 + k_2)) - (b_1s + k_1) \cdot (b_1s + k_1) \quad (9)$$

Taking the inverse of matrix, A, by using its determinant Δ and multiplying the inputs $U(s)$ and $W(s)$ with $1/\Delta$ one obtains

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_1(s) \\ X_2(s) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\Delta} \begin{bmatrix} (m_2s^2 + (b_1 + b_2)s + (k_1 + k_2)) & (b_1s + k_1) \\ (b_1s + k_1) & (m_1s^2 + b_1s + k_1) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U(s) \\ (b_2s + k_2)W(s) - U(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_1(s) \\ X_2(s) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{\Delta} \begin{bmatrix} (m_2s^2 + b_2s + k_2) & (b_1b_2s^2 + (b_1k_2 + b_2k_1)s + k_1k_2) \\ -m_1s^2 & (m_1b_2s^3 + (m_1k_2 + b_1b_2)s^2 + (b_1k_2 + b_2k_1)s + k_1k_2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U(s) \\ W(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

When only the study of input $U(s)$ is needed, one can set $W(s) = 0$. As a result, the transfer function $G_1(s)$ is given as

$$G_1(s) = \frac{X_1(s) - X_2(s)}{U(s)} = \frac{(m_1 + m_2)s^2 + b_2s + k_2}{\Delta} \quad (12)$$

When the study of the disturbance $W(s)$ is of interest, one sets $U(s) = 0$ obtaining the transfer function $G_2(s)$ as

$$G_2(s) = \frac{X_1(s) - X_2(s)}{W(s)} = \frac{-m_1b_2s^3 - m_1k_2s^2}{\Delta} \quad (13)$$

The transfer function of the PID controller $G_c(s)$ is given as

$$G_c(s) = K_p + \frac{K_I}{s} + K_Ds = \frac{K_Ds^2 + K_p s + K_I}{s} \quad (14)$$

where K_p , K_I and K_D are the proportional, the integral and the derivative term respectively, of the PID controller.

The feedback control system with the respective transfer functions for each element (plant, controller and external disturbance) is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The PID controller and the external disturbance.

The transfer function $F(s)$ of the disturbance can be calculated from the block diagram of Figure 4 as follows

$$G_2(s) = F(s)G_1(s) \Leftrightarrow F(s) = \frac{G_2(s)}{G_1(s)} = \frac{\frac{-m_1 b_2 s^3 - m_1 k_2 s^2}{\Delta}}{\frac{(m_1 + m_2)s^2 + b_2 s + k_2}{\Delta}} = \frac{-m_1 b_2 s^3 - m_1 k_2 s^2}{(m_1 + m_2)s^2 + b_2 s + k_2} \quad (15)$$

The three gains of the PID controller, that is, the numerical values for the three terms, were selected with trial and error as $K_P=1200$, $K_I=500$ and $K_D=450$. Several methods, such as the Ziegler-Nichols method, or optimization procedures (e.g. a genetic algorithm) can be also used for the selection and/or fine-tuning of the values for the three terms of the PID controller if necessary. Fuzzy self-tuning can be also used for the calculation of the PID gains as described in [24].

3. Numerical Results

For the simulation of the active suspension, as described in Subsection 2.1, the Simulink package of MATLAB was used. The Simulink models, along with any other necessary file or numerical data for the reproduction of the results of the present investigation (fuzzy controller, data, etc.) are available as supplementary material.

Two different formulations are investigated for the active suspension. The first one considers linear springs, while the second one incorporates nonlinearities in the suspension's springs, as described in Subsection 2.1. In order to simulate the road's bumps, two different types of disturbances are considered: a step-type disturbance $w = -0.1\text{m}$ and a sinusoidal-type disturbance of the form $w(t) = -0.1 \cdot \sin(t) - 0.1\text{m}$.

For the linear case, the three parameters of interest for the passive system (without control), that is the deflection, the velocity and the acceleration are depicted with a straight line (-) in Figures 5, 6 and 7 for the step-type disturbance and in Figures 8, 9 and 10 for the sinusoidal-type disturbance. The maximum and minimum diversion of the deflection, velocity and acceleration of the body from the equilibrium point for the passive system, that is, the one without any control, are given in Table 2 for both disturbances for the linear case.

For the nonlinear case, the deflection, the velocity and the acceleration are depicted with a straight line (-) in Figures 11, 12 and 13 for the step-type disturbance and in Figures 14, 15 and 16 for the sinusoidal-type disturbance.

The diversion of system's parameters for both disturbances for the nonlinear case, are given in Table 4.

A controller based on fuzzy logic was used for the control of these vibrations for both cases. For the linear case, a three-term (PID) controller was also used for comparison.

3.1 Linear active suspension system with fuzzy and PID control

In the first layout, the linear case is considered (see Figure 1(a) and Equations 1 and 2). Two different excitations (step and sinusoidal) are studied. The simulation time is set equal to 5 sec.

The results in terms of suppression of deflection, velocity and acceleration for the active system with fuzzy and PID control for the step-type disturbance are graphically presented in Figures 5, 6 and 7 with a dashed line (--) and a dash-dot line (-.) and respectively. Correspondingly, for the sinusoidal-type road disturbance, the results in terms of deflection, velocity and acceleration are depicted in Figures 8, 9 and 10.

The maximum and minimum diversion of the parameters of interest for the system with the fuzzy and PID controller are given in Table 2. The vibration suppression in terms of deflection, velocity and acceleration for both fuzzy logic and PID control are given in Table 3.

Table 2. Maximum and minimum diversion of the deflection, velocity, and acceleration for the passive, fuzzy and PID systems for the linear suspension under step- and sinusoidal-type disturbance.

		Passive			Fuzzy			PID		
		$x_1 - x_2$ (m)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (m/s)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (m/s ²)	$x_1 - x_2$ (m)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (m/s)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (m/s ²)	$x_1 - x_2$ (m)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (m/s)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (m/s ²)
Step	Max	0.052	0.991	75	0.032	0.655	75	$9.84 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.056	1.47
	Min	-0.049	-0.669	-17.82	-0.036	-0.963	-16.39	$-7.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.049	-1.42
Sinus	Max	0.06	1.06	79.29	0.038	0.767	79.25	0.011	0.062	1.588
	Min	-0.053	-0.69	-23.38	-0.019	-0.342	-18.36	$-7.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-0.526	-1.488

Table 3. Percentages of reduction after the application of fuzzy and PID control for the linear suspension under step- and sinusoidal-type disturbance.

	Passive VS Fuzzy			Passive VS PID		
	$x_1 - x_2$ (%)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (%)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (%)	$x_1 - x_2$ (%)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (%)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (%)
Step	32.79	2.53	1.54	82.38	93.59	96.89
Sinus	49.16	36.67	4.92	83.43	66.08	93.93

3.2 Nonlinear active suspension system with fuzzy control

In the second setup, a nonlinear suspension system (see Figure 1(b) and Equations 3 and 4) is studied under step- and sinusoidal-type road disturbance. The simulation time is again set to 5 sec and the results of fuzzy control in terms of deflection, velocity and acceleration are presented in Figures 11, 12 and 13 for the step-type disturbance and in

Figures 14, 15 and 16 for the sinusoidal-type road bump. The numerical results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Maximum and minimum diversion of the deflection, velocity, and acceleration for the passive and fuzzy systems and percentages of reduction after the application of fuzzy control for the nonlinear suspension under step- and sinusoidal-type disturbance.

		Passive			Fuzzy			Passive VS Fuzzy		
		$x_1 - x_2$ (m)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (m/s)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (m/s ²)	$x_1 - x_2$ (m)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (m/s)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (m/s ²)	$x_1 - x_2$ (%)	$\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$ (%)	$\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$ (%)
Step	Max	0.043	0.738	55	0.024	0.472	55			
	Min	-0.043	-0.527	-	-0.017	-	-	51.99	43.29	9.76
Sinus	Max	0.048	0.828	59.29	0.029	0.526	59.25			
	Min	-0.046	-0.556	-17.34	-0.017	-	-	51.34	43.36	10.44

Figure 5. Deflection ($x_1 - x_2$) of passive (-), fuzzy controlled (--), and PID controlled (-.) linear suspension for step disturbance.

Figure 6. Velocity ($\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$) of passive (-), fuzzy controlled (--), and PID controlled (-.) linear suspension for step disturbance.

Figure 7. Acceleration ($\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$) of passive (-), fuzzy controlled (--), and PID controlled (-.) linear suspension for step disturbance.

Figure 8. Deflection ($x_1 - x_2$) of passive (-), fuzzy controlled (--), and PID controlled (-.) linear suspension for sinusoidal disturbance.

Figure 9. Velocity ($\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$) of passive (-), fuzzy controlled (--), and PID controlled (-.) linear suspension for sinusoidal disturbance.

Figure 10. Acceleration ($\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$) of passive (-), fuzzy controlled (--), and PID controlled (-.) linear suspension for sinusoidal disturbance.

Figure 11. Deflection ($x_1 - x_2$) of passive (-) and fuzzy controlled (--) nonlinear suspension for step disturbance.

Figure 12. Velocity ($\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$) of passive (-) and fuzzy controlled (--) nonlinear suspension for step disturbance.

Figure 13. Acceleration ($\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$) of passive (-) and fuzzy controlled (--) nonlinear suspension for step disturbance.

Figure 14. Deflection ($x_1 - x_2$) of passive (-) and fuzzy controlled (--) nonlinear suspension for sinusoidal disturbance.

Figure 15. Velocity ($\dot{x}_1 - \dot{x}_2$) of passive (-) and fuzzy controlled (--) nonlinear suspension for sinusoidal disturbance.

Figure 16. Acceleration ($\ddot{x}_1 - \ddot{x}_2$) of passive (-) and fuzzy controlled (--) nonlinear suspension for sinusoidal disturbance.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

For the linear suspension, the passive system, that is, the one prior the application of any control, presents significant vibrations. More specifically, the maximum width of these vibrations in terms of deflection, velocity and acceleration is 0.101m, 1.66m/s and 92.82m/s² respectively for the step-type excitation, while for the sinusoidal-type disturbance the corresponding widths read 0.11m, 1.75m/s and 102.67m/s² respectively.

From the numerical experiments of the first control configuration, that is, the one with the fuzzy logic controller, it is demonstrated that the vibrations for all the parameters of interest settle down after 1 second or earlier with a maximum width of 0.068m for the deflection, 1.62m/s and 91.39m/s² for step-type excitation. According to Table 3 there is a reduction of around 33% for deflection and a slight reduction below 3% for the other two parameters. Fuzzy control is more efficient for the sinusoidal disturbance, presenting significant improvement in terms of velocity (37% instead of 2.5%) and slightly better results in terms of deflection (49% instead of 33%) and acceleration (5% instead of 1.5%). In addition, the fuzzy logic controller was proved capable of suppressing the vibrations very quickly in every case.

Correspondingly, in the case where the PID controller is used, the maximum deflection width for step excitation is 0.018m, which is significantly lower than the corresponding value of fuzzy controller (82% reduction instead of 33%). However, the damping is much slower. As can be seen for example in Figure 5, the deflection does not settle down completely within the 5 secs. of simulation, but instead, it follows the one of the passive system after 2.5 sec. Velocity and acceleration are reduced by more than 90%, however again the vibrations are not totally suppressed. A similar behavior is observed for the sinusoidal-type disturbance, although the performance of fuzzy logic controller has been improved.

For the case of the non-linear suspension, the widths of vibrations of the passive system in terms of deflection, velocity and acceleration are measured to be 0.086m, 1.27m/s and 71.27m/s² respectively for the step disturbance while the maximum widths for sinusoidal-type road are 0.094m, 1.38m/s and 76.63m/s² respectively.

Fuzzy logic controller seems to be very efficient in this case, especially in terms of deflection and velocity with reductions around to 50% and again within 1 sec. of simulation. In any case, further tuning of fuzzy parameters is necessary for the improvement of the control behavior.

For the linear case, one can observe that the active suspension, which is controlled by a fuzzy system, damps the vibrations, which are caused by both step- and sinusoidal-type road abnormalities, significantly faster compared to the one which is equipped with a PID controller. More specifically, the fuzzy controller manages to reduce the vibrations in less than 1 sec. for every case examined, while almost 5 secs. or more are required by the PID system for the same assignment. However, PID control seem to work smoother, especially in the first one to two seconds, as the width of vibrations within this time frame is significantly smaller for all the three variables of interest, that is the deflection, the velocity and the acceleration.

For the nonlinear case, the fuzzy controller seems to work even better with significant improvement of the percentages of reduction of the examined parameters. This observation is in accordance with the results reported in [20].

The problem of the non-smooth behavior of the fuzzy controller in terms of velocity and especially acceleration is known and can be overcome using adaptive neuro-fuzzy schemes (e.g. ANFIS) as for example in [25] or genetic algorithms [14]. However, this way the complexity and the computational cost of the system will be increased, which for the case of an industrial application it may not be desirable.

Nonetheless, a hybrid scheme based on the combination of fuzzy systems and PID control may provide better results and thus, it can be an object of further study. Moreover, this hybrid control scheme can be optimized using neural networks, genetic algorithms, or other nature inspired optimization methods, if necessary, taking into account the previous comment about complexity. In another direction, for more severe disturbances, loss of contact between the wheel and the road would introduce an additional nonlinearity with consequences in the quality and safety of ride. This effect could be studied in a future work.

The theory and software used for this paper are available in the open academic book [26].

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Conflict of interests

The authors confirm that there is no conflict of interests associated with this publication and there is no financial fund for this work that can affect the research outcomes.

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